

FARM-LEVEL INTERDISCIPLINARY APPROACHES TO ENDEMIC LIVESTOCK DISEASE (FIELD)

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FIELD response to Defra Animal Health and Welfare Pathway – Mandatory Proposals Consultation Document (published February 2026)

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The FIELD Project

The following response draws on research conducted as part of FIELD (<https://field-wt.co.uk>) a 5-year, Wellcome-Trust funded research project on endemic livestock disease involving a consortium of 6 institutions (Hull, Glasgow, Edinburgh, Newcastle, Lincoln and Leeds-Trinity). This substantive project brought a team of social scientists, historians, economists and epidemiologists together, generating novel interdisciplinary insights on two endemic conditions, BVD and lameness. An advisory board for the project included Defra and the Scottish Government. [Grant Ref: 209818/Z/17/Z].

FIELD response to Defra Consultation

Question 51. Please provide any comments or evidence you feel should be considered concerning the socio-economic impact the proposed policy may have on both producers and consumers.

The proposed benefits (both monetised and non-monetised) of the AHWR assume farmer capacity to implement recommended changes as a result of the mandatory vet visit. Our research with farmers identified how their individual circumstances and contexts can impact their capacity to enact change:

- Our survey work and interviews with farmers revealed complexities in their understandings and responses to animal health and welfare issues (Mahon et al, 2021). Differentiation (between scale, system and location of farm; or by an animal's particular breed, age, value or function) makes a substantial difference to farmers' perspectives on animal health and welfare, and consequently decision-making. Therefore, in planning solutions, we argue that it is important that solutions are tailored to particular farms, farmers and animals. In many circumstances the 'ideal'/'best practice' measures suggested by vets and within current farming advice literature are challenging to implement because of complex on-farm situations, including competing demands for attention, time or money or external factors such as climate impacts, increasing costs and public debate.
- Vets and other advisors need to be aware of these complexities when implementing specific recommendations around endemic diseases, and of trying to change behaviours and practices. It is important to incentivise health planning as an ongoing process of improvement not a hurdle or

tick box, with management plans adaptable to the individual farm context and the financial costs of implementation (Mahon et al, 2021).

- Previous research has identified a lack of farmer knowledge as a barrier to improved animal health and welfare. Our research instead revealed farmers are in fact seeking, acquiring and sharing knowledge practices related to the management of animal health, however individual circumstance and context influence how this translates in practice. Suggesting that poor health and welfare is due to a lack of knowledge is reductive and therefore may be alienating. Farmers consult many, varied sources and evaluate the usefulness of these to their own contexts. Barriers to care include resource constraints and a lack of practical, convincing evidence. This highlights the importance of integrating different perspectives and knowledges in understanding and responding to endemic health conditions (Clark et al, 2024a).
- Our research highlighted the importance of animal behaviour in animal and endemic disease management. Working with animals can present challenges and dangers to farmers, farm workers and their animals, which needs to be taken into account as part of the AHWR (Holloway et al, 2024). Farmers and farm workers are reliant on livestock learning and conforming with animal management practices to reduce disease (Sayer, 2023).
- There is much weight placed on the farmer and vet in the proposals with insufficient focus on other people involved in implementing health and welfare strategies, including stockmen & women, and labourers, who remain 'hands-on', as well as para-professionals (e.g. hoof trimmers) who are themselves expert and play a key role in animal care. There are historical legacies caused by the effort to make efficiency gains after 1947. This resulted in different norms and expectations re the work done by farmers & farm managers, as compared to stockmen/women, as compared to farm labourers, alongside specialisation and changes to the governance of landscape. From this point, there was deliberate work to formalise agricultural education and disseminate knowledge across all farm types, and sizes, by job and by skill level, which now influences farm and community memory and experience and therefore responses to animal disease. Animals have also helped shape the farm landscape and practice during this time, e.g. via responses to farm building materials, technology & disease management, this is known to livestock handlers and paraprofessionals, but their key role and the specialist knowledges and skills they have of particular communities and areas appears to be missing in the proposals and needs recognising as part of the implementation of the Review.
- Farming is a highly mechanised and technical field, and the intersection of knowledge and technology is important in managing health and welfare. Our research found some farmers using an armoury of tools for addressing and monitoring health and welfare and it is important that this is recognised within the review criteria. Increasing use of artificial intelligence and robotics, in 'digital farming', for example, is likely to be an important future influence on design and implementation of health and welfare strategies, as is the use of digital technologies to aid with record keeping and the sharing of health and welfare information between stakeholders.

Our research with the veterinary profession provides evidence in support of the proposal for mandatory vet visits. Veterinarians spoke about their changing role in relation to animal health and disease management. They increasingly view their role as involving whole herd/flock health planning, and emphasising preventative action, whilst also acknowledging the continuing need for reactive care. Our findings provide useful insights on how vets view their shifting role from less hands-on technical work to coaching or supporting farmers (Proctor et al, 2026).

On the proposals for a mandatory BVD eradication programme, our research with farmers and vets shows BVD is seen as quite straightforward once its presence is known, and options are generally well understood by farmers. Some risks were however identified:

- The (over) dependence on vaccination as part of eradication programmes was questioned by some vets as presenting some important risks;
- The risk of incorrect storage of vaccines by farmers was highlighted;
- The diversity of approaches to testing and vaccinating (i.e. doing one but not both, and problems identified in correctly implementing a vaccination programme);
- Attitudes to testing, vaccination, and the relative importance of culling were found to vary between farming systems and locations.

Finally in considering the impacts of the proposed policy on consumers, our work with consumers revealed high levels of support for public money to support farmers to deliver ‘farm animal health and welfare’ as a public good. An online survey of 521 members of the UK public revealed low awareness of the changing agricultural policy context, but strong support for public money being used to provide public goods, particularly for FAHW. Findings also indicate a need for more effective public communication of farming and FAHW issues from farming stakeholders to ensure public policy in this domain is responsive and accountable to its citizens (Clark et al, 2024b).

References

Mahon N, Clark B, Proctor A, Holloway L. (2021) Exploring farmers’ understanding of and responses to endemic animal health and welfare issues in the UK. *Veterinary Record*, 189(10).

<https://doi.org/10.1002/vetr.941>

Clark B, Proctor A, Mahon N, Holloway L. (2024a) Exploring farmer and advisor lameness management behaviours using the COM-B model of behaviour change. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2024.1258906>

Sayer K. (2023). Out of the reach of cattle? Animal subjectivities shaping the electrical cultures of British livestock farming in the second half of the 20th century. *Journal of Energy History Revue d'Histoire de "Energie*, (8). <http://energyhistory.eu/en/node/329>

Holloway L, Mahon N, Clark B, Proctor A. (2024) Interspecies encounters with endemic health conditions: Co-producing BVD and lameness with cows and sheep in the north of England. *Sociologia Ruralis*, 64(2), 180-201. <https://doi.org/10.1111/soru.12458>

Proctor A, Clark B, Holloway L, Mahon N, Sayer K, Woods A (2026) Vets as authority figures, knowledge brokers, coaches and mentors, in Skipper A, Serlin R and Gray C (eds) *An Introduction to Veterinary Humanities*, CRC Press Oxford, p.255-266. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003368618-30>.

Clark B, Proctor A, Boaitay A, Mahon N, Hanley N, Holloway L.(2024b) Animal health and welfare as a public good: what do the public think?. *Agriculture and Human Values*, 41, 1841–1856.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10460-024-10585-0>